

ELIXIR Commissioned Service - Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP), Computational Resource Allocation Tool Development

M3.4 Data from MGnify with computational resources used for metagenomics assembly

Tier: Science

Priority Area: Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP)

Executive Summary

This work package aims to streamline the allocation of computational resources for metagenomic assemblies by analyzing input data characteristics and developing a machine learning model to predict resource requirements. To support this effort, EMBL-EBI has generously provided data on the computational demands—specifically peak memory usage—of assemblies generated using the MGnify pipeline.

To this end, EMBL-EBI analyzed the nf-core trace files from their MAGs workflow to collect peak memory usage for each processed sample. The resulting data was then transferred to the FAIRyMAGs GitHub repository.

This milestone lays the foundation for developing a tool that automates computational resource allocation. To train a predictive model for estimating the memory required during the assembly stage of the MAGs workflow, both peak memory usage data and sample accessions (which enable the retrieval of the corresponding raw data) are necessary.

The dataset provided by EMBL-EBI includes peak memory usage for over 40,000 samples, including the biom metadata. A subset of this data has already been used to build an initial machine learning model capable of predicting memory requirements with promising results.

The investigation of the features correlating to memory usage, as well as the development of ML models to predict memory usage, will be outlined in D3.4.

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Supporting Documents

The collected dataset from EBI is publicly available in the FairyMAGs GitHub repository (https://github.com/usegalaxy-eu/FAIRyMAGs/blob/main/Kmer-Memory-Predict/input/mgnify_assemblies_stats.csv), containing peak memory usage and accession IDs for 40.000 samples. A script to add SSR accessions to the dataset, which is required to download the samples to Galaxy for further analysis, is also provided (https://github.com/usegalaxy-eu/FAIRyMAGs/blob/main/Kmer-Memory-Predict/add_SSR_to_assembly_stats.ipynb).

A subset of this data was already used to build models that can predict memory requirements for the assembly step (https://github.com/usegalaxy-eu/FAIRyMAGs/blob/main/Kmer-Memory-Predict/kmer_stats_vs_peak_memory.ipynb).

Dissemination Plans

The data is already publicly available via GitHub. This data will be part of the planned publication and will then be disseminated via means required by the Journal, such as Zenodo.